

"THE PHENOMENON OF READING CULTURE: THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS"

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Abstract

In the article, the author explores the phenomenon of reading culture as a complex socio-cultural phenomenon, covering historical, cognitive and communicative aspects. The article pays special attention to the transformation of reading practices in the digital age and the influence of new technologies on reading preferences. The author focuses on the methodological foundations of studying the culture of reading, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive analysis of this phenomenon. The findings may be useful for further research in the humanities and social sciences.

Аннотация

В статье автор исследует феномен культуры чтения как сложное социокультурное явление, охватывающее исторические, когнитивные и коммуникативные аспекты. В статье особое внимание уделяется трансформации практик чтения в цифровую эпоху и влиянию новых технологий на читательские предпочтения. Автор акцентирует внимание на методологических основаниях исследования культуры чтения, подчеркивая необходимость комплексного анализа данного феномена. Полученные выводы могут быть полезны для дальнейших исследований в области гуманитарных и социальных наук.

Key words: reading culture, youth, systematicity and integrity of research, electronic publications, book culture.

Ключевые слова: культура чтения, молодежь, системность и целостность исследования, электронные издания, книжная культура.

Introduction

Analysis of youth perception of the reading process is becoming relevant in connection with the profound social, economic, political and cultural transformations that occurred in the late 20th – early 21st centuries. These changes require not only an interdisciplinary study of reading culture from the standpoint of philosophy, cultural studies, history, psychology, pedagogy,

physiology and computer science, but also an assessment of possible negative consequences for society, as well as the development of strategies for their prevention and elimination.

A study of domestic and foreign scientific works indicates the need to revise existing approaches to the study of reading culture and the education of young people in Uzbekistan. Effective measures to form a reading culture can be developed on the basis of an interdisciplinary analysis (including philosophy, sociology and pedagogy) and the consolidation of efforts of various social groups - scientists, teachers, public figures and parents.

V. Borodina shares a similar opinion, emphasizing that the solution to this problem requires a holistic interdisciplinary approach. The urgent need to systematize the diverse knowledge about reading determines the need to integrate scientific ideas about its various aspects on a new theoretical and methodological basis [1].

E. Melnikova and A. Kirichek also note that the results of studies based on empirical and theoretical data remain unsystematized and require unification into a single conceptual model [2;3].

Main part

The topic of reading in the modern world has become acute and controversial, requiring an objective and impartial analysis. Firstly, it is obvious that the leisure time of young people has changed significantly, and secondly, it is becoming increasingly clear that the assessment of the current state of reading culture is impossible using previously applied methodological approaches. A comprehensive analysis using modern research methods is necessary for a full understanding of modern reading.

Y. Melentieva, relying on Epictetus' idea that philosophising begins with the realisation of one's own powerlessness, emphasises the lack of deep philosophical reflection on modern processes in the sphere of reading. She notes that the lack of a philosophical view and methodological grounding negatively affects scientific approaches to the study of reading within other disciplines. [4]

The results of research conducted by specialists in the field of reading over the last fifteen to twenty years have highlighted the following trend that confirms our thought:

- attitudes towards reading have changed – reading has become pragmatic and utilitarian;
- reading time in free time has decreased;
- readers still prefer mass and entertainment reading;

- electronic media are far ahead of the reader's preference for paper products;
- cultural, educational, aesthetic reading is becoming an elitist pastime.

[5]

It is important to emphasise that the concept of 'reading culture' includes several key components that form its multifaceted essence. These include culture in general, the history of the emergence and development of the book (book culture), the reading process itself, the level of reading literacy, writing, as well as the reader's personality. The study of these elements makes it possible to comprehensively and deeply investigate the phenomenon of reading culture.

B. Vasiliev, considering the book as a source of culture, states that book culture is an integral and significant part of both domestic and world cultural heritage. In the scientific environment it is presented as a multilevel model, which in this case acts in the form of a triune system: a) the sphere of material production (book production), b) the culture of consumption of book products and c) the field of spiritual creativity and intellectual development. [6]

One of the key elements of reading culture is the reading process itself, which is a complex sociocultural phenomenon. Reading is studied within the framework of various scientific disciplines, including literary studies, philosophy, cultural studies, psychology and pedagogy. It contributes to the intellectual development of a person, enriches his knowledge, expands the boundaries of personal experience, helps to master the values of world culture and forms cultural competence, contributing to social adaptation.

Reading not only preserves and transmits the intellectual heritage of society, ensuring the continuity of knowledge and skills, but also serves as a tool for learning about the world, forming moral and spiritual guidelines, training and education. This intellectual and cognitive process plays a crucial role in the development of personality and is an integral element in the formation of intellectual culture, contributing to the formation of a highly developed, humane and spiritual and moral society.

N. Svetlovskaya states that: 'Reading is practically the only reliable way of 'humanisation', as it allows to expand the child's circle of communication limited by real life and, helping him, looking, as in a mirror, into the 'alien' experience, passing the school of mastering 'alien' speech – thoughts, feelings, evaluations – to search and find himself and his place in life.' [7]

Technological innovations make their adjustments in people's lives, and inevitably there is a new format of reading – electronic (screen) reading, which

today becomes one of the most popular and convenient ways of perceiving information. However, the printed book does not lose its importance, continuing to co-exist with digital formats, just as in the Gutenberg era handwritten books co-existed with printed editions for some time. For the moment, they complement each other, not exclude each other.

Reading culture is a complex, dynamic and multifaceted phenomenon that shapes both the individual and society as a whole. It is determined by spiritual and cognitive needs that contribute to the transformation of an individual into a personality. The reading culture of young people is manifested in their reading experience, value attitude to books and level of reading competence.

Thus, reading culture encompasses not only the individual's personal qualities (especially spiritual qualities), but also the influence of society, age characteristics and aspirations. It presupposes a conscious and serious attitude to the reading process, because true reading – whether paper or e-book – is capable of transforming a person.

Reading plays an important role in a person's life, especially a young person, but it is not an end in itself. It is primarily a tool that serves two main purposes: the acquisition of knowledge and the formation of moral values. According to the philosopher-stoic Epictetus: 'Reading a book is not a deed, but preparation for a deed. When there is a case to help a person, it should not hesitate to postpone reading even the most good and useful book. Reading a book should not be for yourself, but for the service of people, for further application of what you read in life.' [8]

'Man is integral, he embodies, personifies in himself the richness of social relations, connections, the entire available level of culture. All the needs, interests, goals of society live, function not in some independent life of their own, they are somehow, whether directly or indirectly, expressed, embodied in the needs, interests, goals, etc. of each particular individual, personality, person. Man, thus, carries in himself a whole social cosmos', – writes philosopher V.Barulin. [9]

Man's comprehension of himself, society as a part of nature and this world is carried out in various types: philosophical, scientific, religious, historical. The set of such cognitive types at different stages of human development in different civilisations and cultures is diverse and different. Each type of cognition has its own special features, specificity, distinguishing it from other types.

One of such means of cognition of the world, linking man with society, nature and other (similar) subjects is his reading culture.

Conclusion

The analysis of reading culture as one of the forms of influence on the worldview, behaviour and spiritual image of young people allows us to draw a number of important conclusions and findings. First of all, in the process of research it was established that reading culture since ancient times has been not only the main indicator of the level of culture of society, but also an integral condition for its development. With the formation and development of reading culture as a substructure of the general culture of man, morality, spirituality of people, their relations to each other, to the environment, values change, and society itself develops.

On the other hand, the rapidly changing world, dynamic development of information culture and society, new economic and socio-cultural changes make their own adjustments in the value orientations and life preferences of young readers. Intensive development of electronic technologies and interactive network space has increased the number of electronic publications, caused the emergence of digital libraries, virtual book clubs, network communities, and numerous websites. And, as a result, the reader's attitude to traditional books has changed. This is not to say that mankind has stopped reading. No. It's just that the reader has moved to another, new, information-technological level. He still remains Homo Legens, the Reading Man, but, as it seems to us, with the addition of electronus – Homo legens electronus.

Promotion of reading to the masses, to the people, formation of high reading culture is the main factor of formation of morality and spirituality of youth, harmoniously developed personality capable of creative, productive and independent orientation in the rapidly developing information society. And until this issue is not fully resolved, it will constantly meet us in life as an obstacle.

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